
Strategic Heuristic-Based Anti-Malware Model for Preventing and Mitigating Malware Threats in Businesses

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Abstract

Detection, prevention and mitigation of malware are important aspects of cybersecurity as the ugly activities of malware attacks can never be overruled. It has created a very big challenge to most industries as they can't strive freely without the fear of cyber threat which malware is a major contributor. Various malware detection techniques, including signature-based, dynamic analysis and behavior-based approaches were diligently reviewed with the intent to preventing malware threats from first principle. This research work provided a heuristic rule-based approach that described, analyzed and classified malware threats and presented a water-tight approach and reliable playground for building a promising anti-malware software application that will put a lasting solution to malware activities with the prime goal of attenuating the effect of malware in our society.

Keywords: Malware, hybrid approach, heuristic-based, behavior-based, antivirus, software.

1. INTRODUCTION

Malware has become a major threat to computer systems, causing a significant loss of data and financial damages. It is designed to disrupt, or gain unauthorized access to computer systems, networks, or devices[1]. Malware remains a persistent threat to computer systems and networks, with the proliferation of new dimension daily [2]. It poses an extraordinary and growing threat across various cyber worlds and getting more complicated as it uses different techniques to exploit weaknesses in computer systems and compromise the integrity of data within a computer network[3]. Traditional malware detection techniques primarily based on signature-based and behavioral-base approaches, have proven inadequate in dealing with the ever evolving and sophisticated nature of modern malware as perpetrators bypass most laid down techniques[4]. The advancement in malware attacks has degenerated to rapid developments in technology and infrastructures [5]. Detection of this attack has drastically left the tradition method into holistic new detection mechanism. Organizations should embrace and enact robust cybersecurity measures to minimize potential losses, which in tune has led to tremendous shift in technological race [6]. The research paper aligns a tactical and strategic method that detects, mitigates and prevents the attack from first principle where the activities of malware are well analyzed and classified to different control units in such a way that every unit reads and masters the behaviour of each entry into any system.

2. TYPES OF MALWARES

Malware can appear in different forms/types and exhibit unique behaviours, traits and characteristics. By thorough description and understanding of various types of malwares, a better look will be holistically given towards this strategic approach.

Figure 1: Type of Malwares

These malware types have caused a tremendous harm to most organizations and businesses in cyberspace today. The damages such as data exfiltration, service disruption, data espionage, identity theft, stealing resources and system damages have set many establishments back from their competitors all over the globe. Numerous efforts being put in place to cushion and mitigate its activities are proving abortive as perpetrators are working very hard to evade detection and continuously carrying out their ugly activities to achieve their wicked intentions.

3. MALWARE ANALYSIS

The analysis goes as far as examining malicious software to understand its behaviour, purpose and potential impact by identifying malware types, its operations, the way it spreads in different environments. Based on the impact and damages caused to known and unknown sectors, adequate and promising counter measures can be developed, by creating strategies to detect, prevent, neutralize and disengage the activities of malware before it explodes.

Table 1: Guide to Description of the Proposed Application

S/N	Malware Type	Description	Mode of Propagation
1	Trojan Horse	Disguises itself as a legitimate program or file, but actually contains a malicious code	Social engineering, Infected software, private software, infected websites, E-mail attachments, Infected USB drive
2	Virus	Replicates itself by attachments to files	Infected file, E-mail attachments, Infected software, Infected websites, Infected USB drive, Network sharing, Vulnerabilities
3	Worms	Replicate and spread to other systems without human interaction	Exploiting vulnerabilities, E-mail attachments, File sharing, Instant messages, Infected Software, infected websites, Infected USB drive
4	Spyware	Secretly monitor's and collects user's data	Infected software, E-mail attachments, Infected websites, Infected Ads, Infected USB drive
5	Adware	Displays unwanted Adverts by often collecting user's data for advertisement	Infected software, Infected website, Infected Ads, E-mail attachments, Infected USB drive
6	Rootkit	Hides itself and other malwares from system which is often used for malicious purpose	Infected Software, Exploit vulnerabilities, Infected Websites, E-mail attachments
7	Keylogger	Records keystrokes often used to steal sensitive data	Infected software, E-mail attachments, Infected Websites, Infected USB drive, Phishing attacks
8	Ransomware	Encrypt files and demand payment for decryption keys	Phishing E-mails, infected software, exploit vulnerabilities, Infected Websites

Here, the activities and behaviour of malware are summarized and a reliable playground for building a promising anti-malware application that will put a lasting solution to malware activities is equally presented. Since the mode of propagation of malware threats have been displayed, it is deemed fit to build an application that showcase the following attributes in their specified units.

Figure 2: Proposed Anti-Malware Application Framework

Run a Simulation

Input / Event

Sender email

badguy@phishy.com

Blocked file extensions (File Agent)

exe x

bat x

vbs x

Figure 3: Anti-malware Simulation Environment

With the intention of building an application that prevents the entrance of any malware type through the analysis made in figures 1 and 2, the design of the application was simulated (Figure 3) to authenticate the rules carried out in figure 2. The system was able to reject attachments from suspicious files and emails, external drives and advertisements, this simulation exercise has proven that malware threats can be prevented from gaining entrance into computer systems before its manifestations as the solution of this problem lies in the hands of users.

4. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a strategic system that regularly updates systems, reject external drives, advertisements, attachments in files and mails and also neutralizes pop-up menus as to cushion the ugly activities of malware. The performance and characteristics of malware threats were carefully evaluated by describing and classifying its behavior and proposed heuristic-based approach that will detect, prevent and also mitigate malware threat in our society. Various malware detection techniques, including signature-based, dynamic analysis and behavior-based approaches were diligently reviewed with the intent to preventing malware threats from first principle by not allowing its entrance into organization's systems will put everlasting end to its activities hence the proposal of a rule-based heuristic approach that combines multiple ideas to improve the accuracy of malware detection. This proposed approach can be used to detect, prevent and mitigate malware in different applications and scenarios, and can be further improved by incorporating new techniques and algorithms.

References

- [1] John OO. Advancements in automated malware analysis: evaluating the efficacy of open-source tools in detecting and mitigating emerging malware threats to US businesses. TX International Journal of Science and Research Archive, 2024, 12(02), 1958–1964 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijstra.2024.12.2.1488>.
- [2] Anupama M, Ammar A. Malware Detection Techniques: A Comprehensive Study. Insights: An International Interdisciplinary Journal. Vol. 01, No. 01, February 2023.
- [3] Jyoti K, Rasika P, Ketan B, Shreya N. Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Algorithms for Malware. Vol 47 issues No 2 October 2024. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385681363>.
- [4] Geeta P, Ruthvik RA, Avinash M, Abhiram A, Koushik V. Decoding cyber threats: advanced techniques in malware detection and analysis. IJCRT2312509 International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT) www.ijcrt.org e562. 2023 IJCRT | Volume 11, Issue 12 December 2023 | ISSN: 2320-2882.
- [5] Badria SA, Dattatreya PM, Meenakshi D, Nidhi J. Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity: Innovations, Threats, and Defense Strategies. Journal of Advanced Zoology ISSN: 0253-7214 Volume 44 Issue S-2 Year 2023 Page 4715:4721.
- [6] Yadigar I and Elshan B (2024) Evasion techniques in malware detection: challenges and countermeasures. Journal of Problems of Information Technology (2024), vol. 15, no. 2, 9-15. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3710-1046>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5940-4136>.